

Development of methodics and modeling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania
ID Nr.100054

The Final Report by

UAB „Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment” and
SIA „Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs”

Client: Aplinkos Apsaugos Agentūra

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Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs

APLINKOS APSAUGOS AGENTŪRA

“AZOTO IR FOSFORO BALANSO IR SUSILAIKYMO SKAIČIAVIMO METODIKŲ BEI PASIŪLYMŲ VANDENS TELKINIŲ APKROVOS TERŠALAIS SKAIČIAVIMO LIETUVOS METODIKAI PARENGIMAS BEI LIETUVOS SITUACIJOS PAGAL PARENGTAS METODIKAS ĮVERTINIMAS“ (PIRKIMO NR. 100054)

the Project is co-financed
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Final Report

by

**UAB “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment” (ELLE)
and
SIA “Procesuālānālies un izpētescentrs” (PAIC)**

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Approved by:

Aplinkosapsaugosagentūra		
M _____	M _____	
Date:	Date	
Signature:	Signature:	

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1. Introduction

The overall objective of the project "Development of methodics and modelling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania" is the assessment of the nitrogen and phosphorus budget by means of the development and subsequent application of the surface water quality modelling system (or model) for the physical territory of Lithuania; use of diffuse semi-parametric model(s) to assess the situation in Lithuania using the simulation system developed (or model) and the integration of the developed simulation system (or model) with the other water models of the Environmental Protection Agency of the Ministry of Environment of the Republic of Lithuania.

The main objective is to meet the requirements of Water Framework Directive and the recommendations of the Helsinki Convention regarding the surface water quality and loads of nutrients into the Baltic Sea.

Lithuanian water quality authorities require efficient and reliable water management, evaluation and forecasting tools to comply with Lithuania's commitments to achieve good water status by 2015 and contribute to the Baltic Sea restoration of good ecological status by 2021. Such tools are water quality modelling systems, which not only allow forecasting of effects of pollution abatement programmes, extreme situations and accidents, but also evaluation of climate change effects on water ecosystems. Implementation and application of such systems are necessary to make sound water management decisions.

Specific objectives of the project are:

1. Select and prepare modelling system (or model) suitable for the modelling nutrient load, retention and concentration of water quality elements such as total nitrogen, total phosphorus, nitrates, ammonium, phosphates, BOD7, dissolved oxygen and sediments;
2. Calculate yearly nutrient loads to water bodies, retention in water bodies and nutrient load apportionment between different sources for the time period of 2000 to 2010 for the Lithuanian territory using modelling system (or model) prepared under the first objective;
3. Prepare GIS based Decision Support Method (DSM) for the identification of critical source areas of nutrient loads and sensitive areas for nitrates;
4. Integrate modelling system (model) prepared under the first objective with the Agency's prepared MIKE 11 model for the main Lithuania's rivers;
5. Integrate modelling system (model) prepared for objective 4 with MIKE 21 the Curonian Lagoon and the Baltic Sea Coast model.

The project commenced on May 31, 2011. Total duration of the project is 16 months.

The project is implemented by SIA "Procesu analizēs un izpētescentrs" (PAIC) in partnership with UAB "Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment".

First Interim report ELLE & PAIC (2012a) was prepared after first 5 months of the project implementation and after round of comments approved by the Project Steering Committee on April 10, 2012. According to the working plan the first reporting phase of the project has covered the activities from A1 to A7 in accordance to the Task 1 "Select and prepare

modeling system (or model) suitable for the modeling nutrient load, retention and concentration of water quality elements such as total nitrogen, total phosphorus, nitrates, ammonium, phosphates, BOD₇, dissolved oxygen and sediments” as defined in the Contract:

- A1 – Selection of the appropriate modelling system
- A2 – Definition of input data sets and mobilization of data
- A3 – Model set-up and calibration for the selected pilot basins
- A4 – Validation, sensitivity and uncertainty analysis
- A5 – Model setup and calibration for Lithuania
- A6 – Training
- A7 - Reporting

The user manual of the water quality modelling system of Lithuania (draft) ELLE & PAIC (2012b) was supplied along with the first interim report.

The 2nd Interim Report was submitted on 3-Aug-2012 - in time based on the revised time schedule for the delivery of the report (letter of the Agency No. (10)-A4-1005 of April 10, 2012). After receipt of the comments by EPA it was resubmitted on 7-Sep-2012. According to the working plan for the 2nd Phase of the project this Report covered

- Task 2. Calculation of yearly nutrient loads to water bodies, retention in water bodies and nutrient load apportionment between different sources for the time period of 2000 to 2010 for the Lithuania territory using modeling system (model) prepared within Stage I (activities A8-A11):

A8 – Input data preparation for Years 2000-2010

A9 – Water quality simulation for 2000 – 2010

A10 – Processing of water quality modeling results for phosphorus and nitrogen (including load separation, calculation of retention)

A11 – Assessment of the loads to the Baltic Sea (including load apportionment, load normalisation)

- Task 3. Preparation of GIS based Decision Support Method (DSM) for the identification of critical source areas (CSA) of nutrient loads and sensitive areas for nitrates (NSA) – activities A12-A14:

A12 – Development of decision support system (including methods for CSA and NSA)

A13 – Preparation of GIS layers

A14 – Reporting

This Final Report of the project is being submitted on 28-Sep-2012 - in time based on the revised time schedule for the delivery of the report (letter of the Agency No. (10)-A4-1005 of April 10, 2012). According to the working plan for the 3rd Phase of the project this Report covers

- Task 4. Integration of modeling system (model) prepared within Stage I with Agency's prepared MIKE 11 model for the main Lithuania's rivers (activities A15-A16):
 - A15 – Integration of water quality modeling system (WQMS) with MIKE 11
 - A16 – Testing of integrated WQMS – MIKE11

- Task 5. Integrate modeling system prepared within Task 4 with the MIKE 21 model for the Curonian Lagoon and the coastal zone of Baltic Sea (activities A17-A19):
 - A17 – Integration of water quality modeling system with MIKE 21
 - A18 – Testing of integrated WQMS – MIKE11 – MIKE21
 - A19 – Final reporting

More detailed description of each activity of each task is provided in the Chapter 2.2, 2.3, 2.4 on activities carried out during the first, second and third reporting periods.

This final report is written in English. A summary of the report in Lithuanian language is provided in Chapter 4.

The continues upgrade of the water quality modelling system developed within Stage I took part during Stages II and III of the project. Therefore the revised user manual of the water quality modelling system of Lithuania ELLE & PAIC (2012d) is attached as a separate volume to this report.

2. Implementation of the Project

2.1. Organisational setup of the project

The project team consists of employees of the consulting Consortium members SIA "Procesuanalīzes un izpētescentrs" (PAIC) in partnership with UAB "Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment" and SIA "Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment" (SIA ELLE).

The project administration and management from the Consortium side is organized by the Project Working Group (WG), which consists of the Project Manager Dr.UldisBethers (PAIC) and partner's responsible person ViktorijaMaceikaitė(UAB "ELLE").

Project scientific leader is Dr.AgritaBriede (PAIC), but the main modelling expert is Juris Seņņikovs (PAIC). The WG has developed the project management scheme, coordinated all team work, approved tasks for experts, controlled and adjusted the relevant issues, including the compliance with the time schedule, reporting and quality assurance.

Project implementation is monitored by the Project Supervision Committee (SC) established by the Agency. The tasks of the SC include evaluation and approval of intermediate and final project reports, initiation of deployment of sanctions, if any breach is noticed in the project implementation schedule, initiation of changes in project activities, monitoring and evaluation of the implementation and achievement of project objectives, provision of recommendations in order to ensure effective implementation of the project.

Whereas seeking to facilitate technical project implementation, a Project Implementation Group (IG) was formed during the kick-off meeting on 9th of May, 2011. The Agency appointed following representatives to the IG:

- Rasa Maslauskaitė, Project Manager from Agency's side, Head of Project Management and Public Procurement Unit;
- SvajūnasPlungė, the leading Technical Coordinator, Chief Specialist and Watershed Modeller;
- AudriusŠepikas, Chief Specialist

The Project IG has frequent technical meetings. UAB "ELLE" is responsible for preparation of minutes of such meetings that are distributed to UldisBethers and SvajūnasPlungė. Official agreed language of technical meetings and minutes of the meetings is English. In the 3rd reporting period one technical meeting was organized. The comments of EPA on the Draft version of the 2nd Interim report were discussed on Aug-27, 2012 (minutes of the meeting attached in AnnexI).

2.2. Activities carried out during the first reporting period

During the first reporting period which covered 5 months period, the following activities have been carried out:

- Selection of appropriate modelling system. More detail description on activities carried out under this task is provided in Chapter 2.2.1. of the 1st Interim Report.
- Definition of input data sets and mobilisation of data is included into the Chapter 2.2.2 of the 1st Interim Report.
- Model setup and calibration for the selected pilot basins. Within this activity the two pilot basins (Graispis and Šušvė) have been agreed and model setup, calibration and validation have been performed for those chosen catchments and agreed time periods. Activities performed under this task are described in Chapter 2.2.3. of the 1st Interim Report.
- Validation, sensitivity and uncertainty analysis is presented in Chapter 2.2.4. of the 1st Interim Report.
- Model setup and calibration for Lithuania. The developed model setup methods allow for preparation of the SWAT model setups for any watershed of Lithuania for the further calculation of N and P loads and fluxes for time period 2000-2010 during the 2nd stage of the project. Description of activities under this task are included into the Chapter 2.2.5. of the 1st Interim Report.

2.3. Activities carried out during the second reporting period

During the second period of the project implementation the following objectives were addressed and activities performed (according to Technical specification):

- The modelling system developed in ELLE&PAIC (2012) was enhanced, see section 2.2.1 of the 2nd Interim Report.
- The water quality modelling system was used for calculation of yearly nutrient loads to water bodies, retention in water bodies and nutrient load apportionment between different sources for the time period of 2000 to 2010 for the Lithuania territory (objective 2.2.2), including the following activities:
 - a. The methodology for the separation of background, non-point agricultural sources and other anthropogenic pollution sources is prepared in Section 2.2.2 of the 2nd Interim Report (activity 2.4.1.1).
 - b. The yearly nutrient loads (from different sources such as background, non-point agricultural pollution, point sources and international pollution) to the surface water bodies of Lithuanian river basin districts for time period of 2000-2010 are calculated and presented in Section 2.2.3 of the 2nd Interim Report (activity 2.4.1.2).
 - c. The nutrient retention in the surface water bodies of Lithuanian river basin districts for 2000-2010 year period is calculated in Section 2.2.4 of the 2nd Interim Report (activity 2.4.1.3).

- d. The methodology for the calculation of source apportionment of riverine loads of the loads to the Baltic Sea was developed in Section 2.2.5 of the 2nd Interim Report (activity 2.4.1.4).
- e. The source apportionment of riverine loads of loads coming to the Baltic Sea for the time period of 2000-2010 is calculated by using prepared methodology in Section 2.2.6 of the 2nd Interim Report (activity 2.4.1.5).
- f. The methodology for the normalization of the nutrient loads by eliminating the influence of hydrometeorological factors (weather and water flows) is recommended and developed in Section 2.2.7 of the 2nd Interim Report (activity 2.4.1.6).
- g. The normalized nutrient load to the Baltic Sea for the period of 2000-2010 is calculated in Section 2.2.8 of the 2nd Interim Report (activity 2.4.1.7).
- h. The evaluation of the results of the calculation of loads to surface water bodies, retention, loads to Baltic Sea, their apportionment and normalization is given in respective Sections – 2.2.3, 2.2.4, 2.2.6 and 2.2.8 of the 2nd Interim Report (activity 2.4.1.8). The set of methodologies in Sections 2.2.2, 2.2.5 and 2.2.7 of the 2nd Interim Report form a technical manual for the calculation of nutrient load, retention, source apportionment of riverine loads and load normalization (activity 2.4.1.9).
- i. The recommendations for the future development of modelling system and methods in regard to the calculation of nutrient load, retention, source apportionment of riverine loads and load normalization (activity 2.4.1.10) are given in concluding remarks (Chapter 3 of the 2nd Interim Report).

The GIS based Decision Support Method (DSM) for the identification of critical source areas of nutrient loads and sensitive areas for nitrates was prepared (objective 2.2.3) including the following activities:

- j. GIS DSM to identify critical nutrient source areas, sensitive nitrate areas and the respective technical documentation for prepared method is given in Section 2.2.9 of the 2nd Interim Report (activity 2.5.1.1).
- k. GIS layer (at a scale of 1:50000) and maps of critical nutrient source areas and nitrate sensitive areas are prepared by using GIS DSM methodology (activity 2.5.1.2).
- l. The recommendations for the future application and development of GIS DSM methodology are given in Section 2.2.10 of the 2nd Interim Report.

2.4. Activities carried out during the third reporting period

During the last – the third –period of the project implementation the following objectives were addressed and activities performed (according to Technical specification):

1. Integration of the water quality modeling system (model) prepared in ELLE&PAIC (2012a) with MIKE 11 model for the major Lithuania rivers provided by the Agency (objective 2.2.4) was performed including the following activities. The results of

activities 2.6.1.1 through 2.6.1.3 are described in Section 2.2.1, whilst activity 2.6.1.4 – in Chapter 3.

- a. Integration of the water quality modeling system (model) prepared in ELLE&PAIC (2012a) with MIKE 11 model for the major Lithuania rivers provided by the Agency is performed (activity 2.6.1.1).
 - b. The possibilities of the integrated modeling system to simulate pollution transport and dispersion during accidents (spill of untreated sewage or oil products) are tested, the test results and subsequent conclusions are supplied (activity 2.6.1.2).
 - c. The technical description (manual) for the application of integrated modeling system for the simulation of pollutant spills is provided (activity 2.6.1.3).
 - d. The recommendations for the future development of modeling system (activity 2.6.1.4) are given in concluding remarks (Chapter 3).
2. Integration of modeling system prepared within Task 4 with the MIKE 21 model for the Curonian Lagoon and the coastal zone of Baltic Sea (objective 2.2.5) was performed including the following activities:
- a. The modeling system prepared within Task 4 with the MIKE 21 model for the Curonian Lagoon and the coastal zone of Baltic Sea is integrated (activity 2.7.1.1) in Section 2.2.2.
 - b. The test of the integrated modeling system is prepared (activity 2.7.1.2) and reported in the same Section.
 - c. The technical description (manual) for the application of integrated modeling system is provided (activity 2.6.1.3).
 - d. The recommendations for the future development of modeling system (activity 2.7.1.4) are given in concluding remarks (Chapter 3).

A summary of the report in Lithuanian language is provided in Chapter 4.

2.4.1. Integration of modelling system with MIKE 11

EPA MIKE11 model

The MIKE11DHI(2008) model setups of main Lithuanian rivers (Akmena-Dane, Bārtuva, Mūša, Nemunas, Šventoji, Venta) were provided electronically by EPA. All setups were prepared (supplied with data, ready to run) for time period 1999 – 2005. The MIKE11 model of main Lithuanian rivers employ the following modeling solutions and the data flows:

1. Hydrodynamic calculations (discharge Q):
 - a. Input for hydrodynamic calculations is formed by DHI Rainfall-Runoff model NAM. NAM model uses the given areas of the catchments contributing to the river.
 - b. A diffuse run-off source is distributed along the pre-divided segments of the river branch.
 - c. Rainfall-Runoff links in MIKE11 are used.
2. Water quality (WQ) modeling:
 - a. The [monthly] measurements at the observation stations are used as the concentrations of substances with the water input from NAM model.
 - b. The nutrient input is also given as diffuse sources along the same segments of the river branch.
 - c. Biggest pollutants are added as additional point sources.
 - d. The water quality model predefined in DHI(2008) Ecolab as „WQlevel4Phos” is used. It calculates the following Ecolab state variables:
 - i. Dissolved oxygen (DO)
 - ii. Temperature (T)
 - iii. Ammonia (NH₄) nitrogen
 - iv. Nitrate (NO₃) nitrogen
 - v. BOD₇ (CBOD)
 - vi. OrthoPhosphate (PO₄)Phosphorus
 - vii. Particulate Phosphorus (ORGP)

Technical manual for integration of SWAT WQMS with MIKE11 and application of integrated system

The essence of the integration of the developed SWAT water quality modeling system with MIKE11 model provided by EPA is in

1. Replacement of the present MIKE11 water input (from precipitation – runoff NAM model) by SWAT water yield.
2. Replacement of the present prescribed nutrient concentrations with the outputs from the SWAT model as well.

There exist two situations for the data transfer between SWAT and MIKE 11 (see Table 1 for a link between SWAT and MIKE11 parameters):

1. Subbasins with direct runoff into the main river (MIKE11 model stretch). If this is the case then the input for Q is SWAT water yield from the subbasin and the concentrations are calculated from a flow of respective nutrients from the subbasin (from HRU level).
2. Inflow into the main river (MIKE11 model stretch) from other rivers. In this case SWAT outputs (river discharge and nutrient concentrations, RCH level) are used as diffuse MIKE11 input given along a very small river segment (20 to 50m).

The necessary temperature input to MIKE11 is taken from the observed data (as in the existing setups).

Table 1. Table of linkage between SWAT and MIKE11 parameters.

SWAT parameters (HRU level)	SWAT parameters (RCH level)	MIKE 11 parameters	Parameter group
WYLD(mm/day)	FLOW_OUT (m ³ /s)	Discharge(m ³ /s)	Discharge
NSURQ(kg/ha/day)	NO3_OUT (kg/day)	NO3(mg/l)	Nitrate nitrogen
NLATQ(kg/ha/day)			
NO3GW(kg/ha/day)			
	NH4_OUT (kg/day)	NH4(mg/l)	Ammonia N
SEDP(kg/ha/day)	MINP_OUT(kg/day)	PO4_P(mg/l)	Phosphate P
ORGP(kg/ha/day)	ORGP_OUT (kg/day)	Particulate_P(mg/l)	Organic P
	CBOD_OUT (kg/day)	BOD7(mg/l)	BOD
	DISOX_OUT (kg/day)	DO(mg/l)	Oxygen
Area (km ²)		Temperature(C)	Other

PAIC_SWAT software PAIC(2012) allows to copy all the data needed and to get the AREA of the subbasins (HRU output has to be aggregated by LandUse and Soil).

The following actions are needed to prepare the MIKE11 input data from the HRU level SWAT results:

- Aggregation of HRU output by LandUse and Soil.
- Summing up nitrate nitrogen SUM (NSURQ,NLATQ,NO3GW).
- The unit conversions:

$$Nutrient \left(\frac{mg}{l} \right) = \frac{Nutrient \left(\frac{kg}{ha*day} \right) * AREA(km^2)}{WYLD(mm/day) * AREA(km^2)} * 100 = \frac{Nutrient \left(\frac{mg}{m^2*day} \right)}{WYLD \left(\frac{m}{day} \right)}$$

$$Discharge \left(\frac{m^3}{s} \right) = \frac{WYLD \left(\frac{mm}{day} \right) * AREA(km^2)}{86.4} = WYLD \left(\frac{m}{s} \right) * AREA(m^2)$$

The unit conversion for nutrients is needed to prepare the MIKE11 input data from the RCH level SWAT results:

$$\text{Nutrient} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{l}} \right) = \frac{\text{Nutrient} \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{day}} \right)}{\text{Discharge} \left(\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{s}} \right) * 86.4} = \frac{\text{Nutrient} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{s}} \right)}{\text{Discharge} \left(\frac{\text{l}}{\text{s}} \right)}$$

To create the MIKE11 boundary condition .DFS0 files one must create a new DFS0 file in MIKE Zero specifying the equidistant calendar axes (see Fig. 4). After it's created the data should be copied into the file and the data type and units – Discharge(m³/s) for discharge and Concentration(mg/l) for nutrients – should be defined.

Step by step data transfer to MIKE11 setup is as follows:

1. Define the diffuse sources in MIKE11. We recommend to use the subbasins between the river tributaries as single diffuse sources, than define a short stretch corresponding to the tributary and so on, moving along the river.
2. Create a RCH input in the place where the MIKE11 setup starts using it as an open inflow.
3. Create the DFS0 files for the boundary conditions.
4. Select the discharge for the HD boundary and corresponding nutrients for the AD boundary from ECOLAB state variables:
 - 1) Dissolved oxygen (DO)
 - 2) Temperature (T)
 - 3) Ammonia (NH4)
 - 4) Nitrate (NO3)
 - 5) BOD (CBOD)
 - 6) OrthoPhosphate (PO4)
 - 7) Particulate Phosphorus (ORGP)
5. Check that the last diffuse inflow ends about 50m before the end of the river (make an interpolated cross-section at this point).
6. Run the model.

Test of the WQMS – MIKE11 integration: modeling setup

The proposed integration of SWAT WQMS – MIKE11 was tested on the example of Akmena_Dane MIKE11 setup. The MIKE11 network of 42,3 km long river stretch is shown in Fig.1.

There are 6 boundary conditions for this MIKE11 setup (see screenshot of boundary condition definition in Fig. 2):

1. Open inflow at the start of the river
2. Fixed water level at the end of the river

3. 3 distributed source inflows (from SWAT)
4. One point source inflow (from the biggest pollutant - Kretinga municipality)

Fig. 1. MIKE 11 river network for Akmena_Dane setup.

An example of data files constituting a single boundary condition point – diffuse inflow is given in Fig.3. It includes HD and AD boundaries, discharge and all the nutrients are from SWAT WQMS, whilst temperature – from observations.

The example of DFS0 file definition is given in Fig.4, whilst the SWAT output data prepared in DFS0 format are shown in Fig.5. Note that DO, BOD, NH4 output from HRU contains very small non-zero values as this input is formally needed but is not provided by SWAT.

Akmena_Dane.bnd11

	Boundary Description	Boundary Type	Branch Name	Chainage	Chainage	Gate ID	Boundary ID
1	Open	Inflow	Akmena_Da	42233.7899	0		1
2	Open	Water Level	Akmena_Da	0	0		2
3	Distributed Source	Inflow	Akmena_Da	28500	42233.7		3
4	Distributed Source	Inflow	Akmena_Da	28000	28500		4
5	Distributed Source	Inflow	Akmena_Da	500	28000		5
6	Point Source	Inflow	Akmena_Da	27800	0		6

Include HD calculation
 Include AD boundaries
 Mike 12

	Data Type	TS Type	File / Value	TS Info	AD boundaries	K-mix
1	Discharge:	TS Fil	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	Dischar	TS-defined	0

	Component Nu	Data Type	TS Type	File / Value	TS Info	Scale Factor
1	1	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	DO	1
2	2	Temperature	TS File	..\..\External Data\ ... Edit	Temperature	1
3	3	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	NH4	1
4	4	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	NO3	1
5	5	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	BOD7	1
6	6	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	PO4_P	1
7	7	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	Particulate_P	1

Fig. 2. Boundary condition definition in MIKE 11 for Akmena_Dane.

Include HD calculation
 Include AD boundaries
 AD - RR
 Mike 12

	Data Type	TS Type	File / Value	TS Info
1	Discharge:	TS Fil	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	Dischar

	Component Nu	Data Type	TS Type	File / Value	TS Info	Scale Factor
1	1	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	DO	1
2	2	Temperature	TS File	..\..\External Data\ ... Edit	Temperature	1
3	3	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	NH4	1
4	4	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	NO3	1
5	5	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	BOD7	1
6	6	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	PO4_P	1
7	7	Concentratio	TS File	..\..\SWAT_OUTPU ... Edit	Particulate_P	1

Fig. 3. Example of boundary conditions – diffuse source inflow.

Fig. 4. Example of DFS0 file created for pasting the SWAT output.

Fig. 5. Example of MIKE11 input file with data from SWAT WQMS.

Test of the WQMS – MIKE11 integration: modeling results

The calculations for Akmena-Dane were performed with the MIKE11 setup using WQMS

input data for three years long time period – from 1-Jan-2002 until 31-Dec-2004.

Fig. 6. Comparison of daily modeling results. SWAT WQMS vs. MIKE11 with SWAT WQMS input. N-NO3 loads at the lower Akmena-Dane.

Fig. 7. Comparison of daily modeling results. SWAT WQMS vs. MIKE11 with SWAT WQMS input. P-PO4 loads at the lower Akmena-Dane.

Fig. 8. Comparison of daily modeling results. MIKE11 with present input vs. MIKE11 with SWAT WQMS input. N-NO3 loads at the lower Akmena-Dane.

Fig. 9. Comparison of daily modeling results. MIKE11 with present input vs. MIKE11 with SWAT WQMS input. P-PO4 loads at the lower Akmena-Dane.

The calculation results are illustrated in Figs. 6-9 as the loads of inorganic nutrients (nitrate nitrogen in Figs. 6, 8 and phosphate phosphorus in Figs. 7, 9) at the lower calculation node of the setups.

The SWAT WQ modelling system is compared with the MIKE11 model which is integrated with SWAT WQMS in Figs. 6-7.

SWAT WQMS overestimates the peak load values of N-NO₃. This is due to the hydraulic model ensures better flow routing in MIKE11.

MIKE11 indicates slower decay (and, thus, is less spiky) of the peak loads of P-PO₄. This is most probably due to the different modeling setup of stream WQ processes.

Both MIKE11 approaches are compared in Figs. 8-9. The totally different approach in both run-off and nutrient load calculation nevertheless lead to surprisingly good match of N-NO₃ loads. The present EPA MIKE11 setup produces much smoother P-PO₄ load time series. One should consider, however that this setup is powered by monthly P-PO₄ measurements in the river.

We may conclude that integration with MIKE11 enhances the SWAT WQMS results in the river. This is mainly because of better hydrodynamic simulation of the transport of substances in the river.

Test of accident spill of untreated sewage

The scenario of considered accident was selected as a spill of untreated sewage from the Kretinga water treatment plant – an existing point source in MIKE11 setup.

Fig. 10. The distribution of N-NH₄ load along the river. 0h after the end of accident.

The spill parameters were chosen for the approximate load matching 70000 people daily nutrient release (i.e. weekly amount for 10 000 people). We simulated 24h long spill on 9-Aug-2004 with water discharge 50000 m³/day, and the following concentrations of nutrients in the effluent: 13.3 mg/l of N-NH₄, 2.7mg/l of N-NO₃, 60mg/l of BOD₇, 1 mg/l of P-PO₄ and 2.3mg/l of P-ORG.

Fig. 11. The distribution of N-NH₄ load along the river. 12h after the end of accident.

Fig. 12. The distribution of N-NH₄ load along the river. 24h after the end of accident.

The distributions of ammonia nitrogen concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) along the river stretch 0, 12, 24 and 36 h after the end of the spill are shown in Figs. 10-13, respectively. The Figures illustrate model representation of the effluent advection, dispersion, diffusion and decay, thus illustrating MIKE11 capability of modeling the emergency situation.

The time-graph of N-NH₄ concentrations at the different locations of the river (given by the distance from the river mouth i.e. the chainage in m) are shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 13. The distribution of N-NH4 load along the river. 36h after the end of accident.

Fig. 14. The time-graph of N-NH4 concentrations at the different locations of the river given by the distance from the river mouth.

2.4.2. Integration of modelling system with MIKE 21

EPA MIKE21 model

The EPA MIKE21 model was assessed during visit to the Klaipėda branch of EPA. The 2D model covers the Curonian lagoon and the coastal zone of the Baltic Sea adjacent to the Lithuania, see Fig. 15 for the modeling domain and bathymetry.

Fig.15. Modeling domain and bathymetry of EPA MIKE11 setup.

The HD and AD components of MIKE21 DHI(2008) are used in the calculations by the model setup for the hydrodynamic (velocity, elevation), temperature and salinity fields. The input data employed are

- Meteorological forcing
- Waterlevel and salinity at the open (sea) boundary
- Inflow (discharge) of 3 rivers: Nemunas, Minija and Akmena-Dane.

The input data files are prepared and the calculations are possible from 1-Jan-2005.

Thus, we may conclude that there is no MIKE21 based water quality model developed at EPA for the Curonian lagoon and coastal zone of Baltic sea. The development, setup and calibration of such a model is far beyond the scope of this project. In the same time we admit that Klaipeda branch of EPA possesses an Ecolab module by DHI and such a water quality

model technically may be prepared.

Technical manual for integration of MIKE21 with SWAT WQMS – MIKE11 and application of the integrated system

If the MIKE21-Ecolab water quality model is developed (not a case in present situation) for the Curonian lagoon and the coastal zone of the Baltic sea then the basis for the integration of the MIKE21 with SWAT WQMS – MIKE11 modeling systems is in the correct use of the MIKE11 result files for prescribing boundary conditions in MIKE21-Ecolab.

We assume that (1) the same "WQlevel4Phos" water quality model is used both for MIKE11 and MIKE21 and (2) both the MIKE11 and MIKE21 hydrodynamic setups remains as at present situation. Then the steps for transferring the boundary conditions are as follows:

- The calculations by SWAT WQMS – MIKE11 modeling system are performed for the time period which covers the time period sought for MIKE21 model run.
- The time series for Q, T, and N-NO₃, N-NH₄, DO, BOD₇, P-PO₄, P-org concentrations are extracted from MIKE11 .res files via MIKE View software DHI (2008) at three locations corresponding to the "q-points" of MIKE11:
 - Minija delta (chainage 160560 m),
 - Nemunas before division of Atmata/Skirvyte (chainage 465413 m),
 - Akmena-Dane delta (chainage 38717 m).
- The unit conversion from µg/m³ to mg/l is performed for the nutrient concentrations.
- Two DFS0 files are created for each of 3 locations
 - Discharge time series.
 - Time series of nutrient concentrations and temperature.
- The prepared DFS0 files are specified as boundary conditions with MIKE21.

Test of the MIKE21 and MIKE11 integration: modeling setup and test results

The proposed integration of MIKE21 – MIKE11 integration was tested on the existing water quality model of MIKE11 and existing hydrodynamical model in MIKE21. The aim of this activity according to technical specifications is to test the modeling system capabilities to evaluate impacts of processes occurring in river basins (changes in land management and pollution abatement measures) and extreme situations (such as spill of untreated sewage or oil products) on the Curonian Lagoon and Baltic Coast hydrodynamics or hydrochemistry.

A hypothetical case study was selected (as described below) to match this aim.

The time periods of the input data available in both modeling systems do not overlap therefore we used the MIKE11 output files starting from 1-Jan-2000 as the input data to the MIKE21 calculation which employs the meteorological forcing (wind) and waterlevel from MIKE21 setup for 1-Jan-2006 onwards.

MIKE21 requires both initial conditions and boundary conditions for water quality parameters. Both were derived by an expert evaluation from the EPA observations in winter period 2006. The initial conditions were applied in all computational domain, whilst boundary conditions at the open Baltic sea boundary. The initial and boundary conditions for the test model run are summarized in Table 2.

Fig. 16. Distribution of N-NO₃ after 7 days of calculation.

We used the water quality model predefined in Ecolab as „WQlevel4Phos” supplied with MIKE11 setups by EPA.

The calculation exercise was performed by the above MIKE21-Ecolab model, from 1-Jan-2006 0:00 until 15-Jan-2006 21:00.

The calculation results are presented as the distributions of concentrations of inorganic nutrients (N-NO₃ in Figs. 16-17 and P-PO₄ in Figs. 18-19) in the modeling domain after 7 days (Figs. 16 and 18) and at the end of the calculations (Figs. 17 and 19).

Table 2. Summary of initial and boundary conditions for MIKE21-Ecolab test setup.

Parameter	Initial condition	Boundary condition
Temperature, degC	1	1
DO, mg/l	14	10
N-NH4, mg/l	0,06	0,02
N-NO3, mg/l	1,5	0,5
BOD7, mg/l	3	1
P-PO4, mg/l	0,05	0,03
P-org, mg/l	0,03	0,02

Fig. 17. Distribution of N-NO3 at the end of calculation period.

The successive distributions of N-NO3 indicate

- rather distinct decrease of nitrate concentration in the bulk of Curonian lagoon,
- evolution (spreading of the nitrate-rich riverine water,
- increase nitrate concentration near the lagoon-sea connection.

Nearly the same general conclusions may be drawn from the distributions of P-PO4.

Fig. 18. Distribution of P-PO4 after 7 days of calculation.

We conclude that the test calculations illustrate the ability to perform the calculations by MIKE21 setup with the use of MIKE21-WQMS outputs. Thus, the modeling system is capable to evaluate impacts of processes occurring in river basins (changes in land management and pollution abatement measures) and extreme situations (such as spill of untreated sewage or oil products) on the Curonian Lagoon and Baltic Coast.

In the same time we admit that in order to benefit from the modeling one should perform a study for the development of water quality modeling system itself for the Curonian lagoon and the coastal zone of Baltic sea. Such a study involves not only the selection of WQ model parameters (via calibration) but also selection of the employed model (parameterization, variables). Further the assumptions related to the setting of the initial and boundary conditions should be analysed.

It is possible that the two ecosystems (of Curonian lagoon and coastal zone of Baltic sea) are highly different even if represented by rather simple WQ model.

The boundary conditions along the huge open boundary at the Baltic sea tends to dominate the solution at the outer domain. The last two considerations raise a question about the possible optimization of the MIKE21 setup by separating the Curonian lagoon into independent modeling domain.

Fig. 19. Distribution of P-PO4 at the end of calculation period.

3. Concluding remarks and compliance with the Working Plan

Critical analysis of problems arisen during project implementation

The minor problems arisen during the project implementation are addressed below in the paragraph "Other recommendations".

The major unforeseen problems were related to the employment of the selected modelling system (SWAT).

- The stand-alone SWAT solver and ArcMap integrated ArcSWAT are not fully compatible.
- The SWAT modelling system is one of the most comprehensive for the process description in the catchments. However, it is rather research oriented and the employment, model development and calibration process is neither user-friendly nor straightforward.
- The SWAT modelling system lacks convenient data visualisation and post-processing tools.

Most of the above problems were solved by development of PAIC-SWAT software PAIC(2012) at the cost of the unexpectedly high personnel resources by the consulting consortium.

Recommendation for the development of WQMS-MIKE11 integrated system

1. We may recommend usage of the MIKE11 hydraulic and water quality modelling (Ecolab) system for the river stretches where it is developed.
2. Along with recommendation (1) we suggest to change the data flows, coupling it with SWAT:
 - a. Substituting precipitation – runoff model NAM with SWAT runoff.
 - b. Substituting existing diffuse sources of pollutants with SWAT outputs.
3. Generally, it would be advisable to upgrade DHI Ecolab software and investigate possibilities to employ more recent water quality modelling schemes.

Recommendation for the development of WQMS-MIKE11-MIKE21 integrated system

The performed tests indicated the the integrated modeling system is capable to evaluate impacts of processes occurring in river basins (changes in land management and pollution abatement measures) and extreme situations (such as spill of untreated sewage or oil products) on the Curonian Lagoon and Baltic Coast hydrodynamics and hydrochemistry.

At the same time we admit that the water quality modelling system for Curonian lagoon and coastal zone of Baltic sea at the moment is non-existent. Therefore the primary recommendation is to develop (create) such a system. It cannot be done without extensive effort of modelling the marine and lagoon ecosystems.

The EPA possesses all means for this (MIKE21 software with Ecolab, developed hydrodynamical model, basis of biogeochemical observations in lagoon and sea), and we may recommend to employ these means. We recommend to use outputs from MIKE11 as

the input data for such a water quality modelling system.

Other recommendations

The recommendations given in the previous reports ELLE&PAIC (2012a, c) are summarised also in the Final report.

Recommendations for data gathering and data processing improvements. The system of the data gathering and processing can be assessed by the contents of the databases supplied by EPA. Therefore our possibilities in recommending improvements are limited to the contents of these databases:

1. The frequency of discharge (waterlevel) observations and water quality sampling in rivers is consistent (once per day / once per month) and need no improvements.
2. Several water quality stations are closed in 2005. We consider this as major downgrade of the observation data series. A general recommendation might be in avoiding changes as much as possible in the list of observed parameters, sampling location and frequency for all stations where data time series are historically available.
3. We recommend to establish monitoring stations on the border – crossing for transboundary rivers (both in- and outflowing) if the catchment area at the border-crossing point exceeds certain value.
4. We recommend to perform additional water quality monitoring campaigns (1) for coverage of unmonitored rivers, (2) to measure water quality parameters upstream and downstream reservoirs. Such non-regular data “points” may improve the situation in combination with the assessment of the model results.
5. We recommend to gather monthly data on water pollution point sources and equalise the set of measured water quality parameters in effluent.
6. The overall quality and consistence of the point source database might be improved.

Recommendations for the future development of prepared modelling system. The further development of the modelling system prepared in ELLE & PAIC (2012a-d) may be recommended taking into consideration:

1. Alternative calibration of SWAT setup for only N and P load calculation (without usage of Qual module for stream processes) might be recommended due the linkage of SWAT with Qual module seems to undergo serious improvements in SWAT community. The modelling of stream processes is possible in MIKE11. Such a recommendation provided in ELLE&PAIC (2012a) is related also to unaccounted loads of nutrients via algae transport into reaches.
2. The routine use and update of the modelling system with actual input data should be performed. We recommend to do this on annual basis.
3. The reconsideration and recalibration of the modelling system is essentially required at regular time intervals (5 to 6 years) in association with (1) improvements in the process description in SWAT models, (2) changes in the land use and management praxis.
4. We recommend continuous work to increase the spatial resolution of the modelling system after this project (i.e. building of SWAT “watersheds” instead of current

“subbasins”). This process has to be performed evolutionary (watershed by watershed) and model calibration procedure has to be used for the critical review of the model input data. The procedures have to be developed for the input data correction (and/or detalisation) if the model calculations indicate the input data quality problems.

5. The systematic review of the input data issues may be performed for the locations where the observations indicate outlying values from the modelling results and/or sudden changes in the time series.
6. We recommend to establish a routine data exchange related to the modelling input data for transboundary catchments with neighbouring countries on annual basis. This includes both the observation data, the geospatial data (land cover, land use etc.) and the statistical data (application of fertilizers, inhabitants, cattle etc.).
7. We recommend continuous work to increase the performance of the model and its input data sets. The results of load, retention and source apportionment calculation may be checked subbasin-by-subbasin to indicate input data problems. These results may be used in combination with the monitoring data. The systematic review of input data issues may be performed for the locations where the observations indicate outlying values from the modelling results and/or sudden changes in the time series.

Recommendations for the future application and development of DSM. Taking into consideration assessment of the available methodologies as well as issues encountered during the application of the two DSM described in ELLE&PAIC (2012c) the following recommendations can be made regarding the future application and development of the DSM aimed at designation of the critical source areas and sensitive nitrate areas:

1. It is necessary to improve the availability and quality of the monitoring data. Such improvements might include increased frequency of samplings, particularly in the regions identified as areas at risk from the water pollution. Besides, sampling times must be aligned at different monitoring sites in order to facilitate such measurement data utilisation in the NVZ designation screening process. Moreover, increased number of samples will permit calculation of 95th percentile and hence allow for exclusion of the extreme values from the monitoring data analysis.
2. It is necessary to review nitrate concentration thresholds defined in the EU Directive (50 mg/l). It is widely acknowledged that this limit is set to high if it is to adequately protect water quality and consequently human health and ecosystems from the adverse impact of the water pollution. Hence it is necessary to define the national standard and limits which will better reflect situation in Lithuania and help to better protect water resources.
3. Identification the country specific pollution thresholds might require detailed assessment on the impact of different pollutants of various habitats and ecosystems. Therefore, it is advisable to carefully identify critical loads specific for various habitats and ecosystems found in Lithuania.

Compliance with working plan

The 3rd phase of the project has been implemented in full compliance with the work schedule proposed in the Technical Proposal and confirmed by the Contract.

Submission of the Final Report has also corresponded to the work schedule and was submitted in timely manner, i.e. September 28, 2012.

The time-table, activities, milestones, deliverables and reports during Stage III of the project are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Activities, milestones, deliverables and reports during Stage III of the project.

Date	Activities	Milestones	Deliverables	Reports
3-Aug				I2D
17-Aug	A15	M9		
31-Aug	A16	M10		
7-Sep				I2
14-Sep	A17	M11		
21-Sep	A18	M12		
17-Aug	A19		D5, D6	FD

Milestones:

M9: Water quality modeling system integrated with MIKE11
M10: Task 4 accomplished
M11: Water quality modeling system integrated with MIKE21
M12: Task 5 accomplished

Deliverables:

D5: Water quality model integrated with MIKE 11
D6: Water quality model integrated with MIKE 21

Reports:

I2D: draft of the 2nd Interim Report
I2: the 2nd Interim Report
FD: draft of the Final Report

4. Summary in Lithuanian / Santrauka lietuviškai

Bendrosios vandens politikos direktyvos ir Helsinkio konvencijos įgyvendinimas iškėlė didžiulius iššūkius Lietuvos institucijoms. Lietuvos įsipareigojimai pasiekti gerą vandens telkinių būklę iki 2012 metų ir prisidėti prie Baltijos jūros geros ekologinės būklės atstatymo iki 2021 metų reikalauja naujų, efektyvių bei patikimų vandens būklės valdymo, vertinimo ir prognozavimo įrankių.

Vieni iš tokių įrankių yra vandens būklės modeliavimo sistemos, kurios ne tik leidžia apskaičiuoti taršos mastus, bet ir prognozuoti taršos mažinimo priemonių, programų, ekstremalių situacijų ir avarijų, žemės naudojimo ir klimato pokyčių įtaką vandens ekosistemoms. Tokių sistemų paruošimas ir įsisavinimas leidžia gauti būtiną informaciją, reikalingą priimti efektyvius vandens valdymo sprendimus.

Šio projekto tikslas – parengti azoto ir fosforo balanso skaičiavimo ir paviršinio vandens kokybės modeliavimo sistemą (modelį) Lietuvos teritorijai paremtą fiziniais, pasklidųjų / pusiau pasklidųjų parametru modeliais, įvertinti Lietuvos situaciją panaudojant parengtą modeliavimo sistemą bei integruoti parengtą modeliavimo sistemą su kitais LR aplinkos ministerijos Aplinkos apsaugos agentūros vandens modeliais.

Specifiniai uždaviniai, iškelti projektui, buvo šie:

1. Modeliavimo sistemos (modelio) parinkimas ir paruošimas azoto ir fosforo apkrovų, susilaikymo ir paviršinio vandens kokybės elementų koncentracijų modeliavimui.
2. Metinių azoto ir fosforo apkrovų, susilaikymo, upių krūvio paskirstymas atskiriems šaltiniams paskaičiavimas 2000-2010 metams Lietuvos teritorijai panaudojant paruoštą, vykdant 1 uždutį, modeliavimo sistemą (modelį).
3. Geografinių informacinių sistemų Sprendimų paramos metodo paruošimas identifikuoti kritines azoto ir fosforo apkrovų šaltinių vietas ir nitratams jautrias vietas.
4. Modeliavimo sistemos (modelio) paruoštos vykdant 1 uždavinį integravimas su Aplinkos apsaugos agentūros parengtu MIKE 11 pagrindinių upių vagų modeliu.
5. Modeliavimo sistemos (modelio) paruoštos vykdant 4 uždavinį integravimas su Aplinkos apsaugos agentūros parengtu MIKE 21 Kuršių marių ir Baltijos jūros pakrantės modeliu.

Sutarties įgyvendinimui pasirinkta jungtinis konsorciumas, kurio nariais yra SIA "Procesu analizės un izpētes centrs" (PAIC) dalyvaujantys partnerystės sutarties pagrindu su UAB "Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment" ir SIA "Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment" (SIA ELLE).

Iš konsorciumo pusės atsakingi už projekto administravimą ir valdymą yra šie asmenys: projekto vadovas Dr. Uldis Bethers (PAIC) ir projekto koordinatore Viktorija Maceikaitė (UAB "ELLE"). Projekto mokslinė vadovė yra Dr. Agrita Briede (PAIC), o pagrindinis ekspertas, atsakingas už modeliavimą - Juris Senņikovs (PAIC).

Siekiant užtikrinti efektyvų ir savalaikį sutarties įvykdymą, projekto valdymo grupė parengė projekto valdymo schemą, koordinavo visos ekspertų komandos darbą, tvirtino ekspertų užduotis, kontroliavo darbų atlikimo, ataskaitų pateikimo grafiką ir užtikrino ataskaitų kokybę.

Projekto įgyvendinimo priežiūrą atlikto Aplinkos apsaugos agentūros įsteigtas Projekto priežiūros komitetas. Šio komiteto užduotys buvo įvertinti ir patvirtinti tarpinius projekto

rezultatus/ataskaitas, inicijuoti projekto veiklų pakeitimus, jei tokių reikėtų, vykdyti projekto įgyvendinimo priežiūrą ir vertinimą, teikti rekomendacijas, siekiant užtikrinti efektyvesnio rezultatų pasiekimo.

Siekiant užtikrinti efektyvesnį projekto įgyvendinimą iš techninės pusės, 2011 m. gegužės 9 d. įvykusio įžanginio susitikimo metu buvo sukurta Projekto įgyvendinimo grupė. Į Projekto įgyvendinimo grupę Agentūra paskyrė šiuos atsakingus asmenis:

- Rasa Maslauskaitė, Projekto vadovė iš Agentūros pusės;
- Svajūnas Plungė, vadovaujantis techninis koordinatorius;
- Audrius Šepikas, vyriausias specialistas.

Oficiali projekto pradžia – 2011 m. gegužės 31 d. Paslaugų teikimo trukmė – 16 mėnesių.

Projektas buvo įgyvendinamas trimis etapais. Kaip buvo numatyta projekto įgyvendinimo grafike pirmoji tarpinė ataskaita pateikta praėjus 5 mėnesiams nuo projekto pradžios. Po Agentūros pastabų pateikimo, pataisius ataskaitą, ši buvo patvirtinta Projekto priežiūros komiteto posėdžio, įvykusio 2012 m. balandžio 10 d., metu. Kaip ir numatyta darbų grafike, pirmasis projekto etapas apėmė šias veiklas, susijusias su užduotimi "Modeliavimo sistemos (modelio) parinkimas ir paruošimas azoto ir fosforo apkrovų, susilaikymo ir paviršinio vandens kokybės elementų (bendrojo azoto (toliau - Nb), bendrojo fosforo (toliau - Pb), nitratinio azoto (toliau - NO₃-N), amonio azoto (toliau - NH₄-N), fosfatinio fosforo (toliau - PO₄-P), biocheminio deguonies suvartojimo per 7 dienas (toliau - BDS₇), ištirpusio deguonies (toliau - O₂) ir sedimentų) koncentracijų modeliavimui".

Įgyvendinant šią užduotį buvo parinkta reikiama modeliavimo sistema (modelis). Tai nemokama SWAT modeliavimo sistema. SWAT (*angl. Soil and Water Assessment Tool* arba *liet. Dirvožemio ir vandens vertinimo įrankis*) pradininkas, sukūręs šį instrumentą, Dr. J. Arnolds iš Teksaso A&M Universiteto Žemės ūkio mokslinių tyrimų tarnybos (*angl. Texas A&M University for USDA Agricultural Research Service*). SWAT – hidrologinis modelis, galintis apibūdinti šiuos procesus bei turintis šias funkcijas (komponentus): oro duomenų valdymas, paviršinės nuotekos, grįžtamieji srautai, filtravimas, išgarinimas, perdavimo praradimai, tvenkiniai ir rezervuarai saugyklos, pasėlių auginimas ir drėkinimas, požeminio vandens srautai, susisiekimo maršrutai, azoto ir fosforo bei pesticidų apkrovos, vandens perdavimai.

Pirmojo projekto įgyvendinimo etapo metu buvo pasirinkta projekto tikslus atitinkanti modelio versija ir parengta platforma modeliavimui. Projekto ekspertai mobilizavo įvesties duomenis, kurie buvo įkelti į atitinkamus modeliavimo sistemos reikalaujamus formatus. Visus reikalingus įvesties duomenis projekto komandai pateikė Aplinkos apsaugos agentūra. Panaudotos šios pagrindinės duomenų grupės:

- Modeliavimo sistemos nustatymams reikalingi duomenys: upių tinklas ir sub-baseinai, skaitmeninis aukščių žemėlapis, dirvožemio ir žemėnaudos šablonai ir parametrai, oro matavimo stotelės, ežerai, tvenkiniai, pelkės ir kt.
- Modelio skaičiavimams reikalingi duomenys: oro stebėjimo duomenys, duomenys apie teršalų išleidimą į upes, žemės ūkio statistiniai duomenys.
- Modelio kalibravimui reikalingi duomenys: nustatyti išleidimai į upes ir vandens kokybės parametrų koncentracijos.

Modelis buvo paruoštas ir sukalibruotas visai Lietuvos teritorijai. Jis apėmė teritorijos

suskirstymą hierarchiniu principu į skaičiavimo vienetus (nuo upių baseinų iki vandenskyrų, sub-baseinų ir hidrologinių charakteristikos vienetų (*angl. hydrological response units (HRU)*) ir parametrų priskyrimą atitinkamiems HRU.

Duomenų bazių naudojimui ir darbui su modeliavimo sistema buvo parengtas procedūrų komplektas. Kartu su šiuo procedūrų komplektu techniniame vartotojo vadove taip pat buvo aprašyti pradiniai modelio sukūrimo žingsniai. Projekto komandos ekspertai pravedė mokymus Aplinkos apsaugos agentūros darbuotojams.

Modeliavimo sistema buvo paruošta, sukalibruota ir pratestuota dviem atrinktiems upių baseinams (Graisupis ir Šušvė). Šiems baseinams taip pat buvo atlikta sukalibruotos modeliavimo sistemos validacija, jautrumo ir neapibrėžtumo analizė 2000-2010 metų laikotarpiui.

Tolimesnis projekto etapas įgyvendinant modeliavimo sistemą buvo skirtas modelio nustatymui bei kalibravimas visai Lietuvos teritorijai. Parengti modeliavimo sistemos nustatymų metodai apėmė tarpvalstybinius klausimus, vandens tekėjimo pasiskirstymą tarp atskirų upių baseinų. Paruošto modelio nustatymo metodai leidžia SWAT modelio nustatymus paruošti bet kuriam Lietuvos upės baseinui, siekiant antrame projekto etape apskaičiuoti azoto ir fosforo apkrovas ir svyravimus 2000-2010 metų laikotarpiui.

Sukalibruotą visai Lietuvos teritorijai modeliavimo sistemą projekto ekspertai įdiegė Aplinkos apsaugos agentūroje esančiame kompiuteryje bei apmokė darbuotojus darbui su šia sistema.

Antrosios tarpinės ataskaitos projektas Agentūrai buvo pateiktas pagal grafiką, t.y. 2012 m. rugpjūčio 3 d. (pateikimo terminas nustatytas Agentūros 2012 m. balandžio 10 d. rašte Nr. (10)-A4-1005). Pataisius ataskaitos projektą pagal Agentūros pastabas, antrasis jos variantas pristatytas 2012 m. rugsėjo 7 d.

Antro projekto įgyvendinimo etapo metu pagrindinis dėmesys buvo skiriamas paskaičiuoti metines azoto ir fosforo apkrovas, susilaikymą, upių krūvio pasiskirstymą atskiriems šaltiniams 2000-2010 metams Lietuvos teritorijai.

Įgyvendinant šią užduotį projekto komanda paruošė įvesties duomenis apie metines azoto ir fosforo taršos apkrovas (iš skirtingų taršos šaltinių) paviršiniams Lietuvos vandens telkiniams 2000-2010 metų laikotarpiui ir išsklaidytų žemės ūkio ir kitų antropogeninės taršos šaltinių atskyrimo metodiką, apdorojo vandens kokybės modeliavimo rezultatus azotui ir fosforui (įskaitant apkrovų atskyrimą ir susilaikymo paskaičiavimą).

Projekto ekspertai paskaičiavo azoto ir fosforo susilaikymą Lietuvos upių baseinų rajonų paviršiniuose vandens telkiniuose 2000-2010 metų laikotarpiu, atsižvelgiant į buferines susilaikymo zonas, ežerus ir pelkes.

Be to, šio etapo metu parengtos metodikos pagalba ekspertai įvertino azoto ir fosforo krūvio, patenkančio į Baltijos jūrą (įskaitant krūvių pasiskirstymą ir normalizavimą) 2000-2010 metų laikotarpiui. Atskyrus žemės ūkio, foninių taršos ir stacionarių šaltinių bei tarpvalstybinių pernašų apkrovas, šios buvo stebėtos per visą upės sistemą.

Azoto ir fosforo krūvio normalizavimui, atmetant hidrometeorologinių faktorių (oro ir vandens srovių) įtaką, parengta rekomendacinė metodologija. Ši metodologija buvo pritaikyta apskaičiuojant normalizuotus azoto ir fosforo krūvius Baltijos jūroje 2000-2010 metų laikotarpiui.

Antroje projekto tarpinėje ataskaitoje pateikti rezultatai apie apskaičiuotus krūvius tenkančius

paviršiniams vandens telkiniams, susilaikymą, į Baltijos jūrą patenkančius krūvius, jų pasiskirstymą ir normalizavimą.

Taip pat antrojo projekto įgyvendinimo etapo metu buvo paruoštas geografinių informacinių sistemų (toliau – GIS) sprendimų paramos metodas, skirtas identifikuoti kritines azoto ir fosforo apkrovų šaltinių vietas bei nitratams jautrias vietas.

Įgyvendinant šią užduotį buvo parengta išsami skirtingose ES šalyse narėse taikomų sprendimų paramos metodų, skirtų nustatyti kritinius azoto ir fosforo apkrovų šaltinius ir nitratams jautrias teritorijas, analizė. Jos rezultatai buvo aprašyti ataskaitoje.

Projekto ekspertai pasiūlė GIS sprendimų paramos metodą, skirtą nustatyti kritines azoto ir fosforo šaltinių vietas (atskirai azotui ir fosforui). Jis buvo pritaikytas apjungiant stebėjimo duomenis ir modeliavimo sistemos rezultatus. Toliau šis metodas buvo pritaikytas visai Lietuvos teritorijai, išskyrus P indekso metodą, kuris buvo pritaikytas tik pasirinktai demonstracinei teritorijai.

Panaudojant GIS sprendimų paramos metodiką buvo paruoštas kritinių azoto ir fosforo apkrovų šaltinių ir nitratams jautrių vietų GIS sluoksnis (mastelis 1:50 000) ir žemėlapiui bei pateiktos rekomendacijos, kaip taikyti šį metodą praktikoje.

Antroje tarpinėje projekto įgyvendinimo ataskaitoje pateikti visi techniniai dokumentai, susiję su paruoštu GIS sprendimų paramos metodu.

Remiantis Agentūros 2012 m. balandžio 10 d. rašte Nr. (10)-A4-1005 pakoreguotu ataskaitų teikimo grafiku, galutinės ataskaitos projektas pateiktas 2012 m. rugsėjo 28 d. (pakoreguota galutinė ataskaita pateikta 2012 m. lapkričio 30 d.). Galutinėje ataskaitoje aprašyta trečio projekto įgyvendinimo etapo veikla, susijusi su Modeliavimo sistemos (modelio) paruoštos vykdant 1 uždavinį integravimu su Aplinkos apsaugos agentūros parengtu MIKE 11 pagrindinių upių vagų modeliu.

Atliekant šią užduotį, projekto ekspertai integravo ankstesnio projekto etapo metu parengtą vandens kokybės modeliavimo sistemą su MIKE 11 sistema pagrindinėms Lietuvos upėms. Ši integracija užtikrina, kad SWAT modelio rezultatai bus naudojami kaip įvesties duomenys (medžiagų srautų atveju) MIKE 11 hidrauliniame ir vandens kokybės modelyje.

Integruota modeliavimo sistema pratestuota, siekiant nustatyti jos galimybes imituoti taršos judėjimą ir sklaidą avarijos atveju (pvz., išsiliejus neišvalytoms nuotekoms ar naftos produktams), testavimo rezultatai aprašyti ir pateiktos išvados. Taip pat ekspertai parengė techninį vadovą, aprašantį kaip taikyti integruotą modeliavimo sistemą taršos išsiliejimas modeliuoti.

Paskutiniame projekto etape taip pat atliktas modeliavimo sistemos integravimas su MIKE21 modeliu, skirtu Kuršių marioms ir Baltijos jūros pakrantės zonai. Atliekant šį darbą buvo paruoštas sistemos testavimas, kuris parodė, jog integruota modeliavimo sistema gali būti naudojama įvertinti baseino teritorijoje atsiradusių pokyčių įtaką Kuršių marių ekosistemai.

Rekomendacijos

Rekomendacijos kaip pagerinti duomenų surinkimą ir apdorojimą. Duomenų surinkimo ir apdorojimo sistemą galima įvertinti tik remiantis Agentūros pateiktu duomenų bazių turiniu:

1. Vandens lygio stebėjimai ir vandens kokybės mėginių ėmimas yra tinkamas (kartą per dieną / kartą per metus).

2. 2005 metais buvo uždaryta keletas vandens kokybės matavimo stočių. Manome, kad tai turėjo neigiamos įtakos stebėjimo duomenų kokybei. Bendra rekomendacija – kiek įmanoma vengti keisti stebimų parametrų sąrašą, mėginių paėmimo vietas ir dažnumą visose stotelėse, kuriose yra sukaupti istoriniai stebėjimų duomenys.
3. Siūlome pastatyti monitoringo stoteles pasienyje ant upių, tekančių tarp valstybių sienų (tiek įtekančiam vandeniui, tiek ištekančiam matuoti), tuo atveju, jeigu upės baseinas pasienio teritorijoje viršija tam tikrą vertę.
4. Rekomenduojame papildomai atlikti vandens kokybės monitoringą tose upėse, kuriose jis nevykdomas bei siekiant išmatuoti vandens kokybės parametrus pasroviui ir prieš srovę nuo vandens telkinių. Tokių ne planinių vietų matavimo duomenys, apjungiant su modelio rezultatų įvertinimu, gali pagerinti bendrą situaciją.
5. Siūlome surinkti mėnesio duomenys iš vandens taršos taškinių šaltinių ir palyginti su išmatuotais nuotekų parametrais.
6. Manome, jog taškinių taršos šaltinių duomenų bazė galėtų būti geresnės kokybės ir nuoseklesnė.

Rekomendacijos dėl tolimesnės paruoštos modeliavimo sistemos plėtros. PAIC ir ELLE paruošta modeliavimo sistema galėtų būti toliau tobulinama:

1. Galima rekomenduoti alternatyvią SWAT struktūros kalibraciją tik azoto ir fosforo krūviams paskaičiuoti.
2. Reikalinga reguliariai naudoti ir papildyti modeliavimo sistemą aktualiais įvesties duomenimis. Rekomenduojame tai daryti kartą metuose.
3. Būtina atlikti modeliavimo sistemos perkalibravimą reguliariais laiko intervalais (kas 5-6 metai), nes tai susiję su (1) SWAT struktūros proceso aprašymo patobulinimais ir (2) pokyčiais, atsiradusiais žemės naudojime ir valdyme.
4. Pasibaigus šiam projektui, rekomenduojame tęsti darbą didinant erdvinę modeliavimo sistemos rezoliuciją.
5. Gali būti atliekama sisteminė įvesties duomenų peržiūra tose vietose, kuriose stebėjimų duomenys skiriasi nuo modeliavimo rezultatų.
6. Rekomenduojame kasmet keisti modeliavimui skirtų įvesties duomenų apskaitą su tarpvalstybinių upių baseinuose esančiomis kaimyninėmis šalimis.
7. Rekomenduojame pastoviai dirbti siekiant pagerinti modelio veikimą ir jo įvesties duomenis. Siekiant nustatyti įvesties duomenų problemas, galima tikrinti apkrovų, sulaikymų ir šaltinių atskyrimo paskaičiavimo rezultatus.

Rekomendacijos dėl tolimesnio Sprendimų paramos metodo taikymo ir plėtros. Atsižvelgiant į esamų metodologijų įvertinimą bei problemas, iškilusias dviejų sprendimų paramos metodų taikymo metu (kaip aprašyta ELLE/PAIC ataskaitoje 2012c), galima pateikti žemiau išvardintas rekomendacijas:

1. Būtina pagerinti monitoringo duomenų kokybę ir prieinamumą. Tarp priemonių gali būti paminėti dažnesni mėginių paėmimai, ypač regionuose, įvardintuose teritorijomis, kurios vandens tarša kelia grėsmę. Mėginių paėmimo dažnumą galima susieti su skirtingomis monitoringo stotelėmis.

2. Būtina peržiūrėti ES direktyvoje nustatytas nitratų koncentracijos ribines vertes (50 mg/l). Pripažįstama, jog nustatyta per aukšta vertė. Taigi, reikėtų nustatyti nacionalinį standartą ir limitus, kurie geriau atspindi Lietuvos situaciją ir padeda apsaugoti vandens išteklius.
3. Siekiant nustatyti specifines taršos ribines vertes šaliai gali prireikti atlikti detalių skirtingų teršalų poveikio buveinėms ir ekosistemoms įvertinimą. Dėl to, rekomenduojama atidžiai nustatyti kritines apkrovas įvairioms Lietuvoje esančioms buveinėms ir ekosistemoms.

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Annex I – Minutes of technical meeting No.3

Project on Development of methodics and modeling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania (ID No.100054)

Minutes of the meeting

Subject: EPA comments on the 2nd Interim Report and the last Stage of project

Date and place: August 27, 2012, Environmental Protection Agency (A.Juozapavičiaus str. 9, Vilnius)

Participants: Svajūnas Plungė, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)
Audrius Šepikas, EPA
Martynas Pankauskas, EPA
Uldis Bethers, SIA "Procesu analizes un izpetes centrs" (PAIC)
Juris Sennikovs, PAIC
Pēteris Bethers, PAIC
Julijs Dubasinska, SIA "Estonian, Latvian & Lithaunian Environment" (ELLE)
Viktorija Maceikaitė, UAB "Estonian, Latvian & Lithaunian Environment"

Discussed and agreed:

1. Time schedule for submission of the draft Final Report –as scheduled on September 30, 2012.
2. Comments presented by EPA on the draft 2nd Interim Report. Each comment was discussed and positions exchanged leading to the agreement on the scope of modifications needed for the acceptance of the report. Detailed Contractor's responses to EPA comments and summary of today's discussions are incorporated into separate letter.
3. It was agreed that modified report in accordance with the agreements reached will be submitted until 7th of September but without modified set-ups.
4. Additional request from EPA side regarding training has been discussed. It was agreed that Juris Sennikovs will spend 1-2 additional days in Vilnius providing training on PAIC SWAT, compilation, scripts, building of setups.
5. Regarding MIKE11 and MIKE21 it was agreed that it may be output files from PAIC SWAT. EPA provided MIKE 11 setup promised to establish contacts with MIKE21 users in Klaipėda.
6. It was confirmed that the work scope for September will cover PAIC SWAT User Manual, set of scripts, further work with model, revised system manual from 1 stage, electronic deliverable of final setups, training, work with MIKE11 and MIKE21)

Detailed technical discussion was organized between S.Plunge, J.Sennikovs and P.Bethers regarding the model system (and EPA comments on it) as delivered along with the 2nd interim report.

Minutes prepared by V.Maceikaitė

Annex II – 1st Interim Report

Annex III – 2nd Interim Report

Volume 1 – User Manual for Water Quality Modeling System for Lithuania